

Funded by
the European Union

Project Acronym	RAISE
Project Name	Research Analysis Identifier SystEm
Project Number	101058479
Topic	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-04
Type of Action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Granting Authority	European Research Executive Agency
Project starting date	1 October 2022
Project end date	31 January 2026
Project duration	40 months

D1.1 Project management and quality control plan

(Version 3.0, 30/11/2022)

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D1.1 Project management and quality control plan

Deliverable Number	D1.1	
Deliverable Name	Project management and quality control plan	
Work Package No	WP1	
Due Date (month)	2	
Submission Date	30/11/2022	
Lead Beneficiary	AUTH	
Version	3.0	
Status	Submitted	
Author name(s)	Maria Spanou (AUTH), Despoina Petsani (AUTH), Pavlina Lazaridou (AUTH), Maria Nikolaidou (AUTH)	
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Keywords	Project management, quality control	
Type	R – Document, report	
Dissemination level	PU - Public	

The **RAISE** Consortium consists of:

Participant #	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
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2 BEN	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	VICOM	ES
3 BEN	NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT SA	INTRA	LU
4 BEN	PANEPISTIMIO DYTIKIS MAKEDONIAS	UOWM	EL
5 BEN	UNIVERSITY OF MACEDONIA	UOM	EL
6 BEN	TECREANDO B.V	TECREANDO	NL
7 BEN	WITA SRL	WITA SRL	IT
8 BEN	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
9 BEN	INNOV-ACTS LIMITED	INNOVACTS	CY
10 BEN	VILABS (CY) LTD	VILABS	CY
11 BEN	KYKLIKI VELTISTOPOIISI IKE	Cyclopt PC	EL
12 BEN	KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET	KI	SE
13 BEN	ATHINA-EREVNITIKO KENTRO KAINOTOMIAS STIS TECHNOLOGIES TIS PLIROFORIAS, TON EPIKOINONION KAI TIS GNOSIS	ATHENA	EL
14 BEN	AINIGMA TECHNOLOGIES	AINIGMA	BE
15 BEN	UNIVERSITEIT HASSELT	UHASSELT	BE
16 BEN	OPENAIRE AMKE	OPENAIRE	EL
17 BEN	CENTRO EUROPEO DI FORMAZIONE E RICERCA IN INGEGNERIA SISMICA	EUCENTRE	IT
18 BEN	ENVE.X SINGLE MEMBER PC	ENVE.X	EL
19 AP	UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHAMPTON	SOTON	UK
20 AP	ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSITY	McGill	CA

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	31/10/2022	Maria Spanou (AUTH)	Table of Contents
0.2	10/11/2022	Maria Spanou, Maria Nikolaidou (AUTH)	Initial draft
0.3	25/11/2022	Despoina Petsani (AUTH)	Contributions and suggested changes
0.4	27/11/2022	Maria Spanou, Despoina Petsani (AUTH)	Formatting and preparation for internal review
0.5	30/11/2022	Pavlina Lazaridou (AUTH), Despoina Petsani (AUTH)	Final changes
1.0	30/11/2022	Despoina Petsani (AUTH)	Document for Internal review
1.1	30/11/2022	Ilias Trochidis (VILABS)	Review
1.2	30/11/2022	Gorka Epelde (VICOM)	Review
2.0	30/11/2022	Despoina Petsani (AUTH)	Integration of reviewers comments
3.0	30/11/2022	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (AUTH)	Final check from the coordinator

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package
PB	Plenary Board or General Assembly

Executive summary

This deliverable outlines the project management framework, quality control procedures and roles required for various managerial and operational activities planned for the RAISE project. It is intended to serve as a set of practical guidelines that help define workflows and rules that will have to be followed by all participants during the project's activities, to ensure the highest quality standards are achieved, and to strengthen the quality management of the project (such as partner responsibilities, quality control mechanisms, documentation control, document formats, and exchange rules).

The report defines the procedures for successfully implementing the project, aiming to maximize collaboration among partners and to clearly define responsibilities among participants. Aside from that, the document specifies the quality, administrative, and communication procedures which the partners are to adhere to during the project's implementation, ensuring full control of the project's development from both a technical and a financial perspective.

Finally, by providing several practical guidelines and rules essential for the day-to-day management of the project, this report complements the provisions of the Grant Agreement and its annexes, as well as the Consortium Agreement, which has already been signed by all beneficiaries.

1 Introduction

1.1 The RAISE Project

The mission of RAISE is to provide the infrastructure for a distributed crowdsourced data processing system, moving from open data to open access data for processing. RAISE will provide the mechanism for sending the algorithm to the dataset instead of sending the data to the algorithm. The real value of open data for the research community is not to access them but to process them as conveniently as possible to reduce time-to-result and increase productivity. RAISE aims at promoting a transparent way of sharing and processing data, enabling the research community to publish their work with evidence-based authenticity of the data-analysis performed, ensuring at the same time the accreditation of their work.

RAISE will be grounded on the fundamental principle defined in the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability). To do so, RAISE brings the processing algorithm (small size) to the dataset (large size) instead of downloading the dataset to the computer where the processing algorithm is. To increase the processing capacity of the dataset repositories, RAISE borrows the crowdsourcing concept where researchers can easily integrate in the existing workflows computers serving both their datasets and the processing capacity.

Figure 1 RAISE Gantt Chart

1.2 Description of WP1

Project management will cover all financial, administrative, scientific, as well as knowledge and innovation aspects. The different Management levels are divided among the WP leaders and include: (1) the project coordinator (AUTH), (2) the quality manager (AUTH), (3) the technical manager

(VICOM), (4) the data protection and security manager (UOWM), (5) the piloting and mobility manager (CERTH), and (6) the dissemination and exploitation manager (VILABS).

The day-to-day activities of RAISE project will be monitored by Project Coordinators, by Work Package Leaders and by the Executive Board. They are supported by the International Advisory Board / External Expert Advisory Board and the Ethics Committee and all accountable to the Plenary Board/General Assembly.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

D1.1 “Project management and quality control plan” includes 7 chapters that discuss and analyse in detail different thematic topics, concerning the RAISE management materials. More specifically:

1. Introduction
2. Project management structure
3. Project management Tools and Guidelines
4. Document management
5. Project reporting and financing
6. Quality assessment
7. Intellectual property right issues

2 Project management structure

2.1 Consortium

The RAISE consortium consists of 20 partners from 10 countries (18 beneficiaries and 2 associated partners: SOTON from UK and McGill from Canada).

The consortium as whole has excellent experience in all the tasks defined for RAISE. In particular, the partners provide the project with technical (AUTH, VICOM, INTRA, CERTH, UoWM, UoM, TCR, WITA, CLPT), scientific (AUTH, VICOM, CERTH, AINIGMA, UoWM, UoM, SOTON, McGill), innovation and exploitation (VILABS, ATHENA, OpenAIRE) experience. The academic partners (AUTH, UoWM, SOTON) have long experience in data sharing and processing and the possible barriers to data fairness. Due to the importance of this issue this proposal became attractive even for International Partners (McGill), working towards realising the RAISE vision.

Technical expertise is a core requirement for RAISE, that is why the consortium covers a great spectrum of technical knowledge including security (UoWM), block chain (WITA), data handling (AUTH, CERTH), system architecture (AUTH, VICOM), system integration, synthetic data (VICOM) and data storage to name a few.

Apart from the technical perspective of RAISE, the scientific partners will conduct research beyond the state of the art on 3 challenging pilot domains (AUTH, VICOM, CERTH, AINIGMA, UHASSELT, EUCENTRE, EnvE.X, MCGILL).

Finally, the RAISE sustainability and integration with EOSC is supported by the partners expertise on product sustainability (VILABS) and existing knowledge of EOSC provided services (ATHENA, OpenAIRE).

In the following table the list of partners is presented:

Short Name	Organisation	Country
1 - AUTH	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	EL
2 - VICOM	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	ES

3 - INTRA	NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT SA	LU
4 - UOWM	PANEPISTIMIO DYTIKIS MAKEDONIAS	EL
6 - TECREANDO	UNIVERSITY OF MACEDONIA	IT
7- WITA SRL	TECREANDO B.V.	EL
8 - CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	EL
9 - INNOV-ACTS	INNOV-ACTS LIMITED	CY
10 - VILABS (CY) LTD	VILABS (CY) LTD	CY
11 - Cyclopt PC	KYKLIKI VELTISTOPOIISI IKE	EL
12 - KI	KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET	SE
13 - ATHENA	ATHINA-EREVNITIKO KENTRO KAINOTOMIAS STIS TECHNOLOGIES TIS PLIROFORIAS, TON EPIKOINONION KAI TIS GNOSIS	EL
14 - AINIGMA	AINIGMA TECHNOLOGIES	BE
15 - UHASSELT	UNIVERSITEIT HASSELT	BE
16 - OPENAIRE AMKE	OPENAIRE AMKE	EL
17 - EUCENTRE	CENTRO EUROPEO DI FORMAZIONE E RICERCA IN INGEGNERIA SISMICA	IT
18 - ENVE.X	ENVE.X SINGLE MEMBER PC	EL
19 - SOTON	UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHAMPTON	UK
20 - McGill	ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSITY	CA

Table 1: RAISE Partners

2.2 Roles and entities

Communication and collaboration among project partners and stakeholders in the stakeholder ecosystem are essential to achieving the project goals. Therefore, specific roles and management entities have been identified:

Project Coordinator (PC) (Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis, AUTH, [linkedin.com/in/evdokimosk/](https://www.linkedin.com/in/evdokimosk/))

The role of the PC is to represent the project and the consortium, report to the Commission, monitor overall project performance, administer project resources, and promote project visibility. The PC will chair the Project Steering Board meetings and is responsible for the project formal communication with the Commission and other stakeholders.

Technical co-ordinator (TC) (Dr. Gorka Epelde, VICOM, [linkedin.com/in/gorkaepelde/](https://www.linkedin.com/in/gorkaepelde/))

The role of the Technical co-ordinator is to audit the R&D performance of the project and ensure accomplishment of the technical objectives. The TC is responsible for resolving work implementation problems and dead ends, and is also the direct link between the Project Management Board and the people performing the work helping to bridge communications between technical and clinical parties.

Scientific co-ordinator (SC) (Prof. Panos Bamidis, AUTH, [linkedin.com/in/panagiotis-bamidis-4281354](https://www.linkedin.com/in/panagiotis-bamidis-4281354))

The role of the Scientific co-ordinator is to audit the Joint Research Activities performance of the project and ensure accomplishment of the scientific objectives

Quality and Risk Manager (QRM) (Prof. Panos Sarigiannidis, UOWM, [linkedin.com/in/panagiotis-sarigiannidis-7636901a](https://www.linkedin.com/in/panagiotis-sarigiannidis-7636901a))

The Quality and Risk Manager is responsible for monitoring the compliance and quality processes and the development of procedures that enhance quality outcomes for the project.

Impact Manager (Despoina Petsani, AUTH, [linkedin.com/in/despoina-petsani](https://www.linkedin.com/in/despoina-petsani))

The role of the Impact Manager is to assure that the design and implementation of the RAISE system will maximise the impact to the end-users (researchers).

International Advisory Board (IAB) /External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB)

The Executive Board will appoint and steer an External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB). The EEAB is responsible for assisting and facilitating the General Assembly in taking decisions. A non-disclosure agreement will be executed between all parties and each member of the EEAB by the Coordinator.

In order to provide insight regarding the project development, RAISE will establish an EEAB that will meet regularly with the consortium throughout the project. The EEAB will consist of people with technical expertise and experience in data handling, sharing, and FAIRness, as well as research expertise. A stakeholder's perspective is important, as is policy capacity to support the sustainability of the system, and advice on the most appropriate steps to be taken to establish a research analytics system within the research community. EEAB will be finalized the first 3 months of the project by the consortium.

Internal Ethical Board

Ethical committee's role is apart from GDPR and technical ethical issues, linking, and enhancing project charter, to share, debate and address ethical issues", but this is not further specified or described.

The Internal Ethical Board will consist of:

- Mr. Panagiotis Kartsidis, AUTH
- Mrs. Maria Nikolaidou, AUTH
- Dr. Gorka Epelde, VICOM
- Prof. Panos Sarigiannidis, UOWM

Additional members from the consortium will be decided during the next general assembly.

Independent Ethical advisor (Maria Iakovidou)

The role of the Independent Ethics Advisor includes the facilitation of ethics compliance by monitoring the project's activities and subsequently providing recommendations to the consortium. Additionally, the IEA will be available to the coordinator for advice in case an activity of the project raises ethical or data protection concerns.

According to "Roles and Functions of Ethics Advisors/Ethics Advisory Boards in EC-funded Projects, 05 July 2021" the role of the IEA is to guide and advise the Project Consortium regarding ethics while monitoring the Project's activities and to make recommendations for future activities. Maria Iakovidou holds an LLB in Law from Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, an LLM in Civil Procedure Law from Democritus University of Thrace and an MSc in Law & Informatics from the Department of Applied Informatics of University of Macedonia and the Faculty of Law of Democritus University of Thrace.

Following her graduation, she worked in the law practice industry as a trainee lawyer and an associate attorney at law. She founded her own law firm in 2011 and she is admitted to practice before the Supreme Court of Greece. She has served as legal counsel of Masoutis S.A.. She is also the legal counsel on data protection issues and the Data Protection Officer (DPO) at Euromedica -Arogi Physical Rehabilitation Center of Thessaloniki since 2019. She is a member of Hellenic Association of Procedural Law since 2016.

Plenary board / General Assembly (PB)

The Plenary Board is the ultimate and main decision body of the project, chaired by the coordinator and consists of the one representative person. It is the Ultimate and main decision body of the project. All will have one single vote, and in case of equal votes, decisive will be the vote of the coordinator. PB will meet once every 3 months.

Executive Board (EB)

The Executive Board shall consist of the:

- Project Coordinator (PC): Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis, AUTH
- Technical co-ordinator (TC): Dr. Gorka Epelde, VICOM
- Scientific co-ordinator (SC): Prof. Panos Bamidis, AUTH
- Quality and Risk Manager (QRM): Prof. Panos Sarigiannidis, UOWM
- WP5 Leader: Dr. Josep Maria Salanova Grau, CERTH
- WP6 Leader: Mr. Ilias Trochidis, VILABS

The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the Executive Board, unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds. The Executive Board shall be responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly. The Executive Board shall monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project. In addition, the Executive Board shall collect information at least every 6 months on the progress of the Project, examine that information to assess the compliance of the Project with the Consortium Plan and, if necessary, propose modifications of the Consortium Plan to the General Assembly.

The Executive Board shall:

- support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables
- prepare the content and timing of press releases and joint publications by the consortium or proposed by the Granting Authority in respect of the procedures of the Grant Agreement Article 17 and Annex 5 Section “Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility” and of Section 8 of this Consortium Agreement.

Work Package Leaders (WPL)

WP nr.	Main Responsible	Deputy
WP1	Evdokimos Konstantinidis	Panagiotis Bamidis
WP2	Despoina Petsani	Maria Spanou
WP3	Panagiotis Sarigiannidis	Nikolaos Katertsidis
WP4	Gorka Epelde	Andoni Beristain
WP5	Josep Maria Salanova Grau	Georgia Aifandopoulou
WP6	Ilias Trochidis	Stella Papasarafianou
WP7	Panos Kartsidis	Alexandra Anagnostopoulou

Table 2: RAISE WP Leaders

2.3 Project Meetings

The purpose of project meetings is to facilitate effective communication among project partners and to ensure that all the project's objectives are achieved. As part of the RAISE project, a series of plenary Consortium meetings, technical meetings and online regular teleconferences will be organized throughout the project's duration. The first plenary meeting took place in Thessaloniki (29-30 November 2022).

2.3.1 Preparation and organisation of meetings

2.3.1.1 Convening meetings:

Each Consortium Body shall be convened by its chairperson.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	At least once a year	At any time upon request of the Executive Board or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly
Executive Board	At least quarterly	At any time upon request of any Member of the Executive Board

2.3.1.2 Notice of a meeting

Each member of a Consortium Body shall be notified in writing of the meeting by the Chairperson of the Consortium Body. It is important that the Consortium Body be informed as soon as possible and no later than the minimum number of days before the meeting as indicated below:

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	45 calendar days	15 calendar days
Executive Board	At least quarterly	At any time upon request of any Member of the Executive Board

2.3.1.3 Sending the agenda

The chairperson of a Consortium Body is responsible for preparing and sending a copy of the report to each member of the Consortium Body. As indicated below, an agenda should be provided no later than the minimum number of days before the meeting.

	Minimum number of days before the meeting
General Assembly	21 calendar days, 10 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Executive Board	7 calendar days

2.3.1.4 Adding agenda items

A Consortium Body's agenda must identify any item requiring a decision by its members. As indicated below, any member of a Consortium Body may add an item to the original agenda on written notice to all other members of the Consortium Body prior to the meeting.

General Assembly	14 calendar days, 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Executive Board	2 calendar days

In the course of a meeting, the Members of a Consortium Body present or represented can unanimously agree to add a new item to the original agenda.

The Consortium Body may also hold meetings via teleconference or videoconference, or by using other telecommunications technology.

2.3.1.5 Decisions without a meeting

A decision may also be taken without a meeting if the following conditions are met:

- a) The Coordinator circulates a suggested decision to all Members of the General Assembly with a deadline for responses of at least 10 calendar days after the Party receives it.
- b) The decision is approved by 51 (or higher) percentage of the parties. All parties will be informed of the results of the vote by the Coordinator. It is possible to submit a veto within 15 calendar days of receiving this information. Following notification to all members by the Coordinator, the decision will become binding. Records of the votes will be kept by the Coordinator and made available to the Parties upon request.

2.3.2 Consortium Plenary Meetings

The Consortium Plenary Meetings are the main opportunity for communication and collaboration within RAISE. All partners will be required to attend the meetings on a regular basis as mentioned above, as this is a contractual requirement. The participating institutions will host the plenary meetings in turn. Alternatively, a substitute or proxy may be appointed to attend and vote on their behalf. As part of consortium meetings, the current work in progress, the work to be completed, next actions will be scheduled, technical issues will be discussed, and solutions will be found, as well as promoting cooperation between partners, addressing integration issues, and updating the vision for the project. Meetings of the consortium may also be conducted by teleconference or other means of communication. Advisory Board members are welcome to attend Consortium meetings upon invitation, but are not entitled to vote.

2.3.3 Information about physical meeting organization and attendance.

As part of each plenary meeting, the consortium should discuss and decide the location and potential dates for the next plenary meeting. It is the responsibility of the hosting organization to find and book an appropriate location for the meeting and inform the consortium at least one (1) month in advance in order to allow time for travel arrangements. In addition, the hosting organization should provide information about how to access the meeting location.

Meetings of each Consortium Body may also be held by tele- or videoconference, or other telecommunication means.

2.3.4 Minutes of meetings

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall produce written minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. The chairperson shall send the draft minutes to all Parties within 20 calendar days of the meeting.

2.3.5 Technical or WP meetings

Aside from Plenary Meetings, partners may also decide to organize face-to-face meetings to focus on a specific Work Package or a specific selection of tasks (either scientific, technical, or other) in order to facilitate effective collaboration and communication between partners and accelerate the development and integration process. In such cases, the Consortium as a whole should be informed,

and either the Project Coordinator or the Technical Coordinator should attend in order to ensure effective coordination with other partners.

2.3.6 WP leaders teleconferencing

RAISE introduces "Stand-Up meetings" which will take place online (teleconferences) every month. The meetings are expected to last no more than 15 minutes. Partners are encouraged to participate, however, only the WP leaders will provide updates on the progress of each WP. The Planner tool in Microsoft Teams will be used to report updates and facilitate stand-up meetings. It will be included in each WP. Minutes of the meeting will be recorded in the Planner.

2.3.7 WP teleconferencing

Work Package leaders are encouraged to conduct stand-up meetings to coordinate the tasks of their respective Work Packages. Online documents, divided into Tasks and sub-tasks (if necessary), shall be produced and used in this case. Minutes of the meeting will be kept in online-shared documents (in Microsoft Teams). For scheduling meetings for different Work Packages, there are predefined Team links (shared with the consortium).

Every partner interested in arranging a virtual meeting can use the link for the meeting of the WP or use the general link if the discussion is not clearly related to a particular WP.

It is the responsibility of the person scheduling the meeting to send an email and notify the attendees, including all of the required information, such as the date, time, and the link to the meeting. Organizers should also add the meeting to the RAISE Google Calendar.

The person organising the meeting can also add the corresponding link to the description and add in the guests the RAISE-HE mailing list.

2.4 Work Packages

A detailed list of RAISE's 7 Work Packages and coordinating partners is presented below.

WP	Work Package Name	WP Leader	Start month	End Month
WP1	Project Management and Coordination	1 - AUTH	1	40
WP2	Requirements Elicitation, Technical and Legal Specifications	1 - AUTH	2	34
WP3	RAI Central Hub - FAIR Data Catalogue Access, and Immutable Research Registration	4 - UOWM	2	40
WP4	RAI Certified Node	2 - VICOM	6	36
WP5	Pilot in real-life cases	8 - CERTH	8	40
WP6	Dissemination, Exploitation, Sustainability and EOSC Integration	10 - VILABS (CY) LTD	1	40
WP7	Ethics requirements	1 - AUTH	1	40

Table 3: RAISE Work Packages

2.5 Planned Milestones

The following milestones have been identified within the project.

Milestone Number	Milestone name	WP number	Delivery date
1	Project setup, stakeholders and system specification development roadmap	WP2, WP1	6
2	Build the RAISE Stakeholder's Network and RAI community	WP2	10
3	First Release of RAI Central Hub	WP3	12
4	Final Release of RAI Central Hub	WP3	40
5	Deployment of 10 RAI Certified Nodes	WP4, WP5	36
6	Make all datasets available to the research community in the RAI Certifies Nodes	WP5	20
7	RAISE system EOSC integration	WP6	40

Table 4: RAISE Milestones

2.6 Planned Deliverables

The following deliverables have been identified within the project

Deliverable number	Deliverable name	WP number	Type	Diss. level	Delivery date
D1.1	Project management and quality control plan	WP1	R — Document, report	PU - Public	2
D1.2	Data management plan	WP1	R — Document, report	PU - Public	6
D2.1	User requirements analysis and RAISE use cases description	WP2	R — Document, report	PU - Public	30
D2.2	Service architecture consumer protection requirements	WP2	R — Document, report	PU - Public	20
D3.1	RAI Cloud services' specifications	WP3	R — Document, report	PU - Public	18
D3.2	Research Analysis Identifier (RAI) Handbook	WP3	OTHER	PU - Public	18

D3.3	RAI Central Hub and Visual Analytics	WP3	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	35
D4.1	RAI Certified Node virtual machine image	WP4	R — Document, report	PU - Public	32
D4.2	Data Plagiarism Checker results	WP4	R — Document, report	PU - Public	10
D4.3	Code security and quality assessment	WP4	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36
D5.1	RAI system impact assessment in real-life use cases	WP5	R — Document, report	PU - Public	40
D6.1	Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	WP6	R — Document, report	PU - Public	6
D6.2	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report (first version)	WP6	R — Document, report	PU - Public	18
D6.3	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report (final version)	WP6	R — Document, report	PU - Public	40
D7.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	WP7	ETHICS	SEN - Sensitive	1

Table 5 RAISE Deliverables

2.7 Effort per Work Package

The effort estimated per each partner id presented below:

Partner	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7
1 - AUTH	19.00	20.00	32.00	30.00	24.00	9.00	
2 - VICOM	3.00	4.00	22.00	31.00	10.00	5.00	
3 - INTRA	1.00	1.00	10.00	7.00	2.00	2.00	
4 - UOWM	2.00	3.00	33.00	15.00	2.00	4.00	
5 - UOM	1.00	1.00	6.00	14.00	3.00	2.00	
6 - TECREANDO	1.00	4.00	14.00	12.00	7.00	2.00	

7 - WITA SRL	1.00		16.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	
8 - CERTH	3.00	6.00	14.00	6.00	26.00	5.00	
9 - INNOV-ACTS	1.00	11.00	2.00		5.00	4.00	
10 - VILABS (CY) LTD	5.00	8.00			16.00	28.00	
11 - Cyclopt PC	1.00	4.00	8.00	15.00	2.00	2.00	
12 - KI	1.00	2.00			10.00	3.00	
13 - ATHENA	1.00	3.00		11.00	2.00	6.00	
14 - AINIGMA	1.00	2.00			10.00	2.00	
15 - UHASSELT	1.00	1.00			8.00	1.00	
16 - OPENAIRE AMKE	1.00		3.00	3.00		6.00	
17 - EUCENTRE	1.00	4.00			15.00	3.00	
18 - ENVE.X	1.00	4.00			16.00	3.00	
19 - SOTON	1.00	2.00	4.00	11.00	1.00	2.00	

Table 6 RAISE Partners' Effort per Work Package

3 Project Management Tools and Guidelines

To accomplish the management of the project documents including reports, the Coordinator in collaboration with the RAISE consortium has chosen and established several management tools and guidelines to be followed throughout the project.

Quality Assurance Procedure and Assessment: The final approval of all generated documents must follow a specific procedure. Each deliverable will be evaluated by a select group of partners, and such partners will be listed on the deliverables. The Table of Contents for each deliverable is prepared and shared with the consortium by the Deliverable leader. The leader is responsible for organising and requesting contributions from consortium partners and setting a deadline for delivery that will allow enough time for integration of contributions and refinements. The deliverable is sent to the internal reviewers at least 15 days prior to the submission date. The reviewers are responsible for delivering the review 7 days prior to the submission. The deliverable leader undertakes the task to address reviewers' comments and apply the required changes based on reviewers' comments. The Leader sends the finalized deliverable to the coordination team. The coordinator does the final check and submission.

Conflict Resolution: In order to minimize conflict chances, the above procedures have been described. To resolve any conflict, the PC will need to talk to the involved parties to find an amicable solution. In the event that a resolution is not reached, the issue will be resolved by a majority vote of the Executive Board. The Executive Board may exclude any partner who fails to perform by a vote of unanimity minus one if the offending partner fails to perform. The provisions of the Grant Agreement guidelines and relevant CA provisions will apply in such circumstances. Executive Board members will, however, use their proven negotiation skills to the fullest extent possible before using these procedures.

3.1 Project management tools

3.1.1 MS Teams

All project members will use a web-based Document Management Tool (MS Teams) supported by the TC and QRM. Each Work Package has its own folder, named after the number and the responsible party.

There are four tabs within each WP folder. WP Deliverables and Tasks are included in the corresponding Tasks in a Planner view, which includes columns for Not Started, In Progress, On Hold, Delayed, Closed Tasks. The WP leader assigns a responsible person to each Task and Deliverable.

Each WP has its own files under the Files tab. All deliverables should be uploaded in the files folder inside a folder entitled "Deliverables". It is the WP leader's responsibility to organize the rest of the items in the files folder.

3.1.2 Tools used for code implementation

The following tools used for implementation:

- For code management, GIT software versioning will be used and the gitlab product has been adopted. Currently, WP3-WP4 participants have been granted access. Repositories will be defined as needs are identified.
- Partners must upload source code to Gitlab
- For each feature to implement, start by implementing a mock version which implements the interface with other components with hardcoded behaviour¹ (to promote early integration testing).
- Should use gitflow:
 - Master is used for stable releases (finishing a milestone)
 - Develop is for the latest, yet working software
 - One branch per issue to implement, which is merged to develop. Periodically rebase Master.
- All repositories need to have unit tests with automatic testing provided by Gitlab
- All repositories need to have a readme.md in the root showing how to run the code and describing the content
- It is suggested to have a LICENSE.txt file in the root
- Repositories must be runnable using docker. A docker file in the root is mandatory
- It is suggested to use the git submodule concept to share features among repositories
- There will be a "headquarters" repository to contain general documentation of the solution and other general tools.

3.1.3 Information about how technical developers report and manage issues

- Only each repository leader can create issues.
- When reporting an issue about another partner component, create an issue in your repository and mention the proper partner from the other component. But do not generate issues in his repository directly.
- Use the Gitlab group issue templates to report issues (one for features, the other for bugs...)
- There will be a high-level bug-reporting platform for non-technical users. The coordinators will manage that list and then manage it with technical partners.

¹ <https://www.earnest.com/blog/developing-and-testing-with-mountebank/>

3.1.4 Information about how Pilots – non-technical users report and manage issues

- For the issues reporting and technical developers support an issue tracker (specific technological solution to be determined, candidates include Jira and Gitlab Issues) will be set up within Task 5.1.
- Task 5.1 leaders will collate, aggregate, and prioritize reported issues, which will be analysed and discussed with WP3-WP4 technical meetings for relevance, possible solutions and timeline according to existing milestones.

3.1.5 API description / Message schema definition

- Among different modules with integration needs, APIs will be defined and described so that different development actors have a reference to test their systems communications.
- Message schema definition: Data exchange formats will be described in (json) schema format to be able to validate different modules independently.

3.1.6 Planned methodology for integration

- For each milestone (e.g., sprint) an integration test must be designed and implemented so that it can be automatically launched inside Gitlab. It could be contained in the “headquarters” repository and follow the tools/practices of combining docker-compose (to launch all involved components from their repository or the Gitlab Group container repository)² with behavior-driven-development (BDD and cucumber³).
- Integration testing will be done incrementally: Each partner, while implementing his part, will use continuous integration to test against a mock-up of the non-yet-available rest of the components from other partners.
- Once integration testing succeeds, issued branches need to be merged to develop and if the milestone is achieved, the rebasing of the master branch is needed. Next, all technical partners decide on the next step and define the new integration test.
- In addition to automatic integration testing, some support of manual testing, especially to collect user feedback for the next milestone is crucial. The design, management and result collection will be handled outside of the scope of Gitlab. Then, the results will be reviewed to define the next “integration test” for new features to implement/refine. This process is repeated until the end of the project.

3.1.7 E-mail communication

In order to facilitate communication within the project, mailing lists have been established. The most appropriate communication channel for partners should be the Teams channel in order to prevent redundant and excessive communication. A mailing list for the RAISE Project is available at raise-he-2021@googlegroups.com.

3.1.8 E-mail standards and suggestions.

Below are some instructions regarding the subject line of an e-mail. Every email that is sent among consortium members is in accordance with the project's objectives:

- **Must** include the prefix [RAISE] before the main subject.
- **It is advised** to include the corresponding WP number.
- **It is advised** to include the prefix [Doodle] if a doodle link for a meeting is shared in this email.

² <https://pypi.org/project/pytest-docker-compose/>

³ <https://mohammed-abouzahr.medium.com/integration-test-starter-with-ci-5037410817ee>

- **It is advised** to include the prefix [Action required] if the sender requests any specific action to be taken.
- **It is advised** to include the prefix [URGENT] for any issues requiring immediate attention from the receivers.

3.1.9 Communication within the consortium

For the organization of virtual meetings, teleconferencing (audio- or video-based) will be used. Consequently, Skype may be used for meetings involving a few participants, while Microsoft Teams will be used for larger project online meetings. This channel will also be used to share files among partners.

As part of the WP1 folder in Microsoft Teams, there is a tab that is titled "RAISE_team_contacts", where all the consortium members' information can be found.

To maintain awareness of the project developments, it is useful to keep the project management team in cc of the bilateral communication in order to arrange better flow of information.

3.2 Scientific Publications

The purpose of publications is to describe technologies, algorithms, or methodologies developed within a project. A scientific article may consist of a scientific paper, a book chapter, a book, a poster at a conference, a slide presentation at a conference, a PhD thesis, a public report, a press release, or a news item.

The entire RAISE Consortium must approve all papers submitted for publication in conferences, journals, or media. If a publication is to be submitted, the consortium should be informed as soon as possible. The following procedure ensures that no paper will be submitted without the knowledge of the consortium, that the project will not be misrepresented, and that no confidential information will be unintentionally disclosed. Should one or more partners choose to patent information that is then disclosed, this may generate criticism and, ultimately, damage.

A Publication Review Board (PRB) is established under the RAISE project, which will consist of a Project Coordinator (PC), a Scientific Coordinator (SC), Technical Coordinator (TC) and Quality and Risk Manager (QRM).

Among the duties and responsibilities of a lead author are the following:

- Leader of the writing group is the lead author.
- A manuscript or abstract should be drafted by the lead author.
- It is the lead author's responsibility to ensure that proper and clear communication takes place within the writing group. A manuscript/abstract draft should clearly state the conditions under which it must be written in accordance with the guidelines and instructions for authors of the target journal/conference, as well as the feedback required, as well as a clear deadline for submission.
- During the writing period, the lead author is responsible for monitoring progress and ensuring that co-authors have complied with the full conditions of authorship.
- Lead authors correspond with the Journal's Editors (unless otherwise negotiated) and coordinate the required work following review.
- As the lead author, you are responsible for informing the PRB and the writing group of the final approval of the submitted publication by the Journal's Editor(s).
- It is the responsibility of the lead author to forward the published version of the paper to the PRB and the writing group.

Lead author is the first author. The author is responsible for the manuscript or abstract. In this case, the last author will be considered a special position, i.e., one assigned to the senior supervising researcher. If no other arrangements have been made, this can be the principal investigator of RAISE, Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis.

Submission of a paper involves the following steps:

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- The lead author submits the manuscript to the PRB for approval,
- Following initial submission, the PRB will review the proposal and notify the lead author of their decision within two (2) days.
- It is the lead author's responsibility to contact WP leaders and lead investigators regarding the proposed publication with the intention of inviting them to act as co-authors or to name a suitable co-author in accordance with the guidelines outlined below.
- Whenever a manuscript is submitted to a journal, the lead investigator/author must notify the PRB electronically.
- Once a manuscript has been peer-reviewed by the Journal's reviewers, the lead investigator/author is responsible for revising the manuscript and notifying the PRB upon re-submission.
- As soon as a manuscript is accepted for publication, the lead author is responsible for notifying the PRB and for sending a PDF (Portable Document Format) version to the PRB and WP leader for dissemination.
- In the event that a manuscript is rejected for publication, the lead author is again responsible for notifying the PRB and sending a copy of the journal's justification for rejection.
- Lead investigators/authors are responsible for notifying the PRB and WP6 leader whenever abstracts are submitted to conferences and whether they have been accepted (including whether an oral or poster presentation is planned) or rejected.
- Additionally, a copy of the PowerPoint or poster presentation of the accepted abstract must be sent to the PRB WP6 leader for dissemination and archiving.

The lead author of an accepted publication is responsible for submitting the following information to the EU portal as well.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "New publication" with a dark header bar. Below the header, there is a instruction: "Please provide a DOI for the publication (recommended) or fill-in manually the required information." The form consists of several rows of input fields and checkboxes. Fields include: DOI (text), Type of publication (dropdown), Repository Link (text), Link to the publication (text), Title (large text area), Authors (large text area), Title of the Journal/Proceedings/Books series/Book (text), Number, date or frequency of the Journal/Proceedings/Book (text), Relevant Pages (text), ISBN (text), Publisher (text), Place of publication (text), and Year of publication (text). There are also three radio button questions: "Is this publication available in Open-Access, or will it be made available?" (with options for Green Open Access, Gold Open Access, and No), "Is this a peer-reviewed publication?" (with Yes/No options), and "Is this a joint public/private publication?" (with Yes/No options). A legend indicates that red asterisks denote mandatory fields. At the bottom, there are "Add publication" and "Cancel" buttons.

Figure 5 Required info from publications for reporting in EU portal

The majority of scientific papers are derived from the work done in RAISE towards achieving specific project objectives. Authorship of scientific papers should normally include the following:

- Work Package members and Work Package Task Leaders involved in the data collection and analysis.

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- Leader of a Work Package (usually one individual, but more if their contribution warrants it).
- Scientific Coordinator (usually one individual, but more if their contributions are justified)
- Project Coordinator (usually one person, but more if their contribution justifies it).

Whenever data from RAISE is published or personnel are employed through RAISE, the grant funding the project should be cited as follows:

RAISE - Research Analysis Identifier SystEm– is funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme of the European Union for Research Innovation. Grant agreement number: 101058479

Further information of acknowledgement of EU funding can be found here: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/acknowledge-funding_en.htm

All publication should also respect the Guidelines on **Open Access to Scientific Publications** and Research Data in Horizon 2020 found here : https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

3.3 Dissemination

3.3.1 Project Branding

In order to build the RAISE brand, it is essential to design and create an appropriate logo in order to ensure recognition and communicate the project's identity to stakeholders and the general public. Therefore, all RAISE dissemination materials, documents, presentations at events and conferences, and online channels should include a high quality and prominent logo for the project. Figure 2 illustrates RAISE logos in both vertical and horizontal formats.

Figure 2 RAISE logo

The RAISE project logo is available on the project's collaboration tool, Microsoft Teams, under WP6 channel's files, in the Dissemination and Communication Material, in the folder RAISE logo.

3.3.2 Project website – Social media channels

One of the most crucial tools for the successful dissemination and communication of the results of RAISE project will be the project website, whose first version launched on M1 of the project (October 2022) and is accessible at the following url: <https://raise-science.eu>. All the necessary information regarding the progress of the project as well as project news, materials, etc. will be uploaded there. It will also serve as the hub through which the user groups will be able to find and access the outputs of the project. The website has been developed to contain information about the progress of the project at different stages in order to communicate and expand its results. It will be informative, user-friendly, and accessible. It should engage simple language without technical and highly sophisticated terms. The homepage of the website is presented in 3 below.

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Figure 3: Screenshot of the homepage

RAISE uses Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn. The links of the RAISE social media channels are the following:

- **Twitter:** <https://twitter.com/RaiseScience>
- **LinkedIn:** <https://www.linkedin.com/company/raise-science/>
- **Facebook:** <https://www.facebook.com/raise.science>

Partners are expected to follow RAISE’s social media pages (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn), monitor the announcements and posts, “like” them, comment on them, make their own posts on RAISE’s social media accounts, connect with people, and initiate dialogues or take part in them.

3.4 Performance metrics

The RAISE KPIs are presented in the following.

KPI#	Responsible partners	Description
1.1	ATHENA	RAI datasets are perceived as FAIR (based on DANS FAIR data tool assessment or ARDC FAIR Data self-assessment tool) > 80% of the RAI system users
1.2	AUTH	RAI services are perceived as effective, efficient, and open > 70% of the users/researchers
2.1	VILABS	Create additional Nodes, except the ones provided by consortium partners, during the project lifetime > 3 more Nodes
2.2	VILABS	Registration in the RAI Blockchain server > 50 registrations (1 st year), 100 (2nd year), 200 (3rd year)
3.1	CERTH	Publications with the RAI > 10 publications
3.2	VICOM	Reuse of analysis in new datasets automatically >20 code reuses
3.3	ATHENA	RAI Plagiarism Checker delivered in T4.4 (M22)
4.1	AUTH	The RAI is adopted by at least 1 publishing organization for the publication process

4.2	AUTH	The RAI is adopted by at least 1 publishing organization for the review process
5.1	AUTH	Perceived usefulness of the RAI system > 80% (SUS questionnaire)
5.2	CERTH	Willingness of the researchers to share their data for processing through the RAISE platform >80% of the participating researchers
5.3	VICOM	Reduce time for completing an analysis and publication >40% reduction
6.1	INNOV-ACTS	RAISE services increase the users and usage of EOSC platform >10% by the end of the project
7.1	AUTH	Qualitative measures of approval for the provided analytics of the RAI system (interviews with researchers, WP2)
7.2	VICOM	Reduction of resources needed for the whole pathway of data analysis (send algorithms instead of transferring datasets) >80 %
8.1	CERTH	Number of publications from real-life pilots with RAI >15
8.2	VILABS	Total number of stakeholders engaged in the RAI community >200
8.3	VILABS	Total number of researchers taking part in datathons >200
9.1	VILABS	Number of RIs and SMEs/companies using the RAI system >20
9.2	AUTH	Number of RIs and SMEs/companies participating in the RAI community >50

Table 7 RAISE Partners' Effort per Work Package

4 Document management

4.1 Classification of Documents

Deliverables (which include documents), must always be classified in the following dissemination level categories, using one of the following codes, as stated in the GA:

- PU: Public.
- SEN – Sensitive.

4.2 Document standards

4.2.1 Allowed document types

Working documents intended for subsequent modification by partners should be produced using Microsoft Office (preferably version 2007 or later). Final versions of documents (e.g., internal, and public deliverables) should be published as .PDF documents (compatible with Adobe Acrobat 7.0 or

later). All other (graphics, audio, and video) files should be based on recognized standards: .JPG, .PNG, .GIF, .TIFF, .PPT etc.

4.2.2 Format and style guidelines

The following sections should be included in each document:

- A document-specific cover page: this shall include the title of the document, the main author(s), dates of interest and the version of the document.
- A following page with, amongst others, details on the Project ID, the dissemination level of the document, all contributing authors and an abstract- keywords section (in case the document is a deliverable - report).
- The Table of Contents (ToC).
- Abbreviations List (where applicable).
- An Executive summary.
- The Main body of the text: All sections of the main body of the text should be clearly defined. Section headings, titles and subtitles should be used to structure the document and help the reader maintain an overview of what is being addressed and at what level of detail. Used in conjunction with the ToC, relevant sections can easily be identified for ease of browsing. Figures, tables and graphs contained in the body of the document should be properly explained and their relevance clearly demonstrated. Discussion documents that are not fully formatted should at least clearly distinguish between main sections, titles and running text.
- References and (where applicable) Annexes - Appendices.
- Styles and colour schemes provided in the document templates should be followed.

Documents that are deliverables (reports), should be named accordingly, with additional numbers for version updates and standard suffixes to indicate the format of the document, as stated in Section 4.3 below. It is recommended that the final version be made available as a .PDF file. In the case of intermediate versions of the document, Microsoft Word (or Microsoft PowerPoint) files should be provided since these are much easier to annotate.

Furthermore, in accordance with article 17 of the GA, any dissemination of results (in any form) must display the EU emblem. The EU emblem must be given appropriate prominence when displayed alongside another logo. Additionally, the following statement should be included: "Funded by the European Union". In draft versions of documents prepared by authors from different sites, it is recommended to include the names of the authors as annotations for each section, in order to facilitate communication between the parties involved.

4.2.3 Compliance with Data Protection Guidelines

The Final Deliverables that are specified as "PU: Public" will be uploaded on the Project Website following a data protection quality check and adequate editing. As a result of this revision or editing, the consortium will be able to comply with the requirements or regulations set by the European Union's data protection laws, including the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) that is scheduled to take effect on May 25, 2018.

4.3 Versioning

Documents are developed under the supervision of the person responsible for them [member of the Lead Beneficiary according to the Description of Action (DoA)] who will assign subsections to other contributors, provide clear instructions, and define deadlines, integrate sections into the main document, and maintain the appropriate version control system.

There are three types of intermediate versions that may be produced during the elaboration of a document:

- Working/discussion document setting out main headlines and some elaboration on specific topics.
- Full draft with all the sections nearly complete.

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- Ready-for-review version provided to the internal reviewers for major/minor comments and changes.
- Pre-final version available only for minor changes and to be circulated among the RAISE partners and provided to the PC for final approval, before submitting the document as a deliverable to the EC.

For each of these versions, more than one round of feedback may be required before the final version is developed. When modifying the document, the Microsoft Word Revision Mode should be switched on to record and track all changes. The amended version should be uploaded to the file repository with the appropriate naming convention. Those changes will be incorporated into the present version by the person responsible for the deliverable.

The numbering of versions shall be made as follows:

- Version 0.00 to 0.XX for draft versions of working documents
- Version 1.00 for the version submitted for internal review
- Version 2.00 for the version submitted following reviews and relevant revisions
- Version 3.00 for the version uploaded to the European Commission portal
- Version “3.00_Open” for the version uploaded to the RAISE website taking into account Data Protection Regulation

4.4 Templates

Clean and functional document and presentation templates were developed at the beginning of the project to maintain coherence among the many different documents produced. The following templates for RAISE project documents have been created and made available to the partners:

- Deliverable template
- Deliverable review report template
- Presentation template
- Financial Report template

4.5 Other documents

In the course of the RAISE project, a variety of reports and presentations will be developed. Throughout the RAISE project, each partner is free to produce reports and present on their work. It is important to include the funding sources and acknowledgement of the project. Reports and presentations should be made available to partners upon request. RAISE consortium has agreed on the preparation of internal deliverables (not submitted to the EC) that will facilitate the sharing of information within the consortium and continuous reporting of ongoing developments.

5 Project reporting and financing

The Grant Agreement signed by the RAISE consortium (Nr. 101058479) specifies the terms and conditions applicable to the grant awarded to beneficiaries. The activities funded are the ones described in Annex 1 (Part A and Part B) of the Grant Agreement.

5.1 Eligible Activities

The eligible activities of the RAISE project are defined in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement and entail all necessary actions by the consortium in order to successfully implement the project.

5.2 Eligible Costs

The eligible costs of the RAISE project are defined in Article 6 of Chapter 3 of the Grant Agreement (GA) of the RAISE project.

On pages 17-18 of the GA, the **general eligibility conditions** (6.1) are described,

(a) for actual costs

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(b) for unit costs or contributions (if any)

(c) for flat-rate costs or contributions (if any)

(d) for lump sum costs or contributions (if any)

(e) for unit, flat-rate or lump sum costs or contributions according to usual cost accounting practices (if any)

(f) for financing not linked to costs (if any): the results must be achieved or the conditions must be fulfilled as described in the approved Description of the action (DoA - Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement).

In addition, for direct cost categories (e.g., personnel, travel & subsistence, subcontracting and other direct costs) only costs that are directly linked to the action implementation and can therefore be attributed to it directly are eligible. They must not include any indirect costs (i.e., costs that are only indirectly linked to the action, e.g., via cost drivers).

In-kind contributions provided by third parties free of charge may be declared as eligible direct costs by the beneficiaries which use them (under the same conditions as if they were their own, provided that they concern only direct costs and that the third parties and their in-kind contributions are set out in the approved Description of the action – DoA – Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement (or approved ex post in the periodic report, if their use does not entail changes to the Agreement which would call into question the decision awarding the grant or breach the principle of equal treatment of applicants; 'simplified approval procedure').

On pages 18-22 of the GA, the specific eligibility conditions for each budget category (6.2), are set for the following:

Direct costs

A. Personnel costs

B. Subcontracting costs

C. Purchase costs

D. Other cost categories

Indirect costs

On pages 22-23 of the GA, the ineligible costs, and contributions (6.3) are described:

(a) costs or contributions that do not comply with the conditions set out above (Article 6.1 and 6.2), in particular:

(b) costs or contributions declared under other EU grants (or grants awarded by an EU Member State, non-EU country or other body implementing the EU budget), except for the following cases:

(c) costs or contributions for staff of a national (or regional/local) administration, for activities that are part of the administration's normal activities (i.e., not undertaken only because of the grant)

(d) costs or contributions (especially travel and subsistence) for staff or representatives of EU institutions, bodies, or agencies

(e) other

On pages 23 of the GA, the consequences of non-compliance (6.4) are stated.

5.3 General procedures and rules for project reporting

According to the RAISE Grant Agreement, the Coordinator must submit technical and financial reports to the Commission on a regular basis.

5.3.1 Reporting Periods

The official reporting periods of the RAISE project are the following:

Report 1 (RP No 1): From Month 1 (October 2022) – Month 12 (September 2023), and Report 1 ought to be sent to the coordinators by the 15th of October 2023

Report 2 (RP No 2): From Month 13 (October 2023) – Month 24 (September 2024), and Report 2 ought to be sent to the coordinators by the 15th of October 2024

Report 3 (RP No 3): From Month 25 (October 2024) – January 2026, and Report 3 ought to be sent to the coordinators by the 15th of February 2026

5.3.2 Reporting process

There are several steps that have been defined in the reporting procedure:

- Partners (beneficiaries) are required to submit a six-month report. Contributions should include periodic reports regarding their institution's dissemination and exploitation activities (conducted during the reporting period) as well as administrative aspects. As a final step, they should maintain a record of their team members' time sheets.
- The WP Leaders are required to submit a description of the work progress made in their WP for the Periodic Progress Reports. WP Leaders are responsible for collecting the necessary information, such as scientific contributions from partners. As a result, WP Leaders must ensure and support a well-functioning communication structure within their working groups.
- Various contributions will be compiled by the Coordinating institution, which will submit a consolidated document to the European Commission.

5.3.3 Financial Report Template

The template that partners need to fill in by the 15th of October 2023, by the 15th of October 2024 and by the 15th of February 2026 will be sent to them by the coordinators in due time.

5.3.4 Effort Report Template

The template that partners need to fill in by the 15th of October 2023, by the 15th of October

5.3.5 Currency

It is required that financial statements be prepared in euro. The costs recorded in beneficiaries' accounts must be converted into euro at the average of the daily exchange rate published in the C series of the Official Journal of the European Union, calculated over the reporting period, for beneficiaries and linked third parties with accounting established in a currency other than the euro.

It is necessary to convert the currency at the average of the monthly accounting rates published on the Commission's website for the corresponding reporting period if no daily euro exchange rate is published in the Official Journal of the European Union for the currency in question.

6 Quality assessment

In this section, the Quality Assessment Plan (QAP) for the RAISE project is presented. Its purpose is to provide a set of requirements and standards, as well as to specify control procedures and actions that will assure a high level of quality in project deliverables and project management. To be more specific, the quality expectations for project deliverables, the responsibilities of project partners, quality control procedures for ensuring their implementation, and the risk management strategy are outlined.

6.1 Quality expectations

In the first instance, the expectations regarding the quality of the project deliverables, as well as the expectations regarding the project management, are outlined. A quality deliverable can generally be identified by its efficiency, feasibility, and sustainability. Among the RAISE deliverables, three categories can be distinguished:

- Documents/Reports (R): The documents should follow a consistent format; therefore, a document template has been developed and will be used throughout the project
- Demonstrator, pilot, prototypes (DEM): These deliverables include software components that should satisfy user requirements in terms of functionality, performance, and stability. Moreover, software components should be extensible and reusable so that adding new features and adjusting functionality can be simplified. An important aspect of software quality is proper documentation, which includes English documentation in the source code to assist developers, as well as detailed user manuals to assist end users.
- Other, that includes technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

An effective project management system ensures that the project progress follows the work plan agreed upon. A successful project requires frequent documentation of progress - both technical and financial - and no delays in communicating with the EC or resolving plausible technical and financial issues. Gantt charts based on the deliverables list (Part A of the Description of Action) will be produced, and periodic project management meetings may be held if necessary (preferably as side meetings during technical meetings to reduce travel costs). Partners will receive copies of the minutes of these meetings.

6.2 Quality responsibilities of consortium members

In addition to its many responsibilities, the PC plays a vital role in ensuring the quality of the project. This involves facilitating communication among partners and ensuring that their information is up-to-date, or ensuring that the documents are organized and presented in an appropriate manner.

PC responsibilities include:

- Maintaining compliance with the obligations of partners
- Submitting the other partners' project deliverables and all other documents required by the GA to the EU in time, in the event that one or more partners are late in submitting them.
- Updating and maintaining the address list of members and other contact persons.
- Providing documents and information related to the project to other parties.
- Providing partners with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the PC whenever such copies or originals are required to present claims to the PC.
- Collecting, reviewing (to ensure consistency), and submitting reports, other deliverables (such as financial statements and related certifications) as required by the European Union.

As a further requirement, each partner must notify the PC, who, in turn, must inform the EC and other partners immediately should any event affecting or delaying the implementation of the project, such as a change in its legal, financial, technical, organisational or ownership situation, have a significant impact or delay on the project.

6.3 Quality assurance and quality control process

In this Section, the quality assurance and quality control processes to be followed are described, so that the quality expectations presented in Section 6.1 are realized.

6.3.1 Quality control of deliverables

All deliverables will be internally reviewed in order to ensure timely production and quality. Some of them may also be reviewed externally. As a result, the following process will be followed:

- RAISE's DoA document identifies the partners responsible for each deliverable. It is the partner's responsibility to designate a person responsible for the deliverable (DR).
- It is the responsibility of the DR to identify potential contributors (with the assistance of the WP Leader and partners, if necessary). As a result, the DR and the contributors will agree on the Table of Contents (ToC) as well as the subtasks each contributor will be responsible for. Contributors and the DR will also agree on a provisional calendar. PCs should receive the ToC and provisional calendar at least six weeks prior to the deadline for the deliverables.

D1.1 Project management and quality control plan

- Internal Reviewers (two per deliverable) have already been assigned for all deliverables based on their expertise. In the case of some strategic deliverables, the decision to submit them to external reviewers (chosen outside of the project) can be taken by the PC in collaboration with the DR and WP Leader. Even if only one contributor requests it, a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) will be signed.
- Contributions will be made by contributors (deadlines will be the responsibility of DR and contributors) according to the provisional calendar. DR is responsible for integrating the contributions.
- The DR will forward the deliverable to the internal reviewers when it reaches a ready-for-review stage (at least three weeks prior to the submission deadline).
- It is expected that the internal reviewers will respond with detailed comments within one week.
- The PC reviews the reviews and determines whether there are any major issues. As soon as major issues arise, the PC, together with the WP Leader and the DR, determine the corrective actions to be taken. Whenever there is a disagreement, the Executive Board makes the final decision.
- The DR is responsible for incorporating the reviewers' comments and revisions into an updated version along with a note or email explaining how they were addressed (at least one week before the deadline).
- Within two days of receiving the revised deliverable, the DR distributes it to the reviewers for approval.
- The reviewers notify the DR whether the deliverable has been accepted or whether there are still issues to be addressed.
- A final version of the document is submitted to the PC for approval.
- It is the PC's responsibility to submit the Deliverable to the EC (by e-mailing the electronic version to the EC Project Officer and uploading the final version to the File Repository). A strict deadline must be adhered to for each step of the entire procedure.
- It is also the responsibility of the EC to audit and assess deliverables.

In particular, the deliverable submission procedure consists of the following steps:

Deliverable submission procedure	
Deadline	30 th OR 31 st of the month
Table of contents	1.5 month prior to final submission
First submission	15th of the month
Review	15th to 22nd of the month
Second submission	27th of the month
Review	Until the 30th of the month
Final submission	30th of the month

Table 1 RAISE Deliverables' submission procedure

As described in Part A of the DoA, documents should be reviewed for style, completeness, presentation, and accomplishment of deliverable objectives. The documents should also be examined for technical validity, soundness, and novelty (when applicable), completeness of results, and comparison with existing works, among other factors.

6.3.2 Quality control of project management

Project management shall be controlled by AUTH, legal, and financial departments, which have considerable experience in EU project participation and coordination.

6.3.3 Technical changes

Whenever there is a need to change the approaches to the realization of the technical aspects of the project, a change request will be submitted to the Technical Coordinator, who will then discuss the implications with both the proposing party and the Executive Board. A major change in the technical approach of a part of the system will be discussed and approved at the next project meeting if it is agreed that it is necessary. EC Project Officers will also be notified of substantial changes through the PC if the changes are evaluated as substantial.

6.4 Risk management

The RAISE consortium is comprised of various independent partner organizations. Due to its complex objectives, it requires the collaboration of many experts from different scientific fields. The successful completion of the project will enhance the reputation of each partner and the individuals associated with them. Due to this, it is in everyone's best interest to resolve the problem at hand, regardless of the organisational independence of the partners. It is critical to manage risks in order to ensure that critical objectives are achieved. An effective risk management process must take into account the sources of cost, schedule, and performance risks, as well as other risks, and specify measures to systematically plan, anticipate, and mitigate these risks in order to minimize their impact on the project.

6.4.1 Risk monitoring and control

In the implementation of RAISE, potential risks will be identified during the project's activities and will be addressed appropriately, thereby minimizing the overall implementation risks. As soon as potential risks are identified, the spiral approach of RAISE implementation ensures that these risks will be appropriately addressed within the following stages, thereby minimizing their probability of being encountered. There is, however, a need for overall risk monitoring and control throughout the project. Therefore, the risk status will be reviewed periodically during Consortium meetings in order to re-examine possible sources of risk, uncover risk sources that were overlooked, and reassess risks that had already been identified. In addition to identifying and evaluating new risks, the WP leaders are responsible for communicating them to the other partners.

Each identified risk source has been assigned a probability of occurrence (Low, Medium, High) and a level of impact on the project (also Low, Medium, High). It is possible to add new risk entries or to update or close those that are already open. When monitored risks become critical, the Executive Board decides on further risk management based on the re-assigned priority and consequences of each risk. An appropriate risk management strategy may range from simple acceptance and monitoring when a risk is judged to be negligible, to developing and implementing risk mitigation plans for risks that are deemed unacceptable, due to their high impact.

To reduce the risk to an acceptable level, the associated WP Leader is responsible for developing and implementing a mitigation plan. An effective risk mitigation plan will address issues such as the development of alternative courses of action, possible workarounds, a schedule for the risk handling activities, performance measures for these activities, and finally, a recommended course of action.

It is important to note that even after a risk mitigation plan has been initiated, the risk will still be monitored, and open actions will be tracked until they have been completed. Although all attempts are made to mitigate a risk, some risks may be unavoidable and become a problem that adversely affects the project. In order to address such risks, project meetings will be scheduled as necessary. As a result of these meetings, appropriate response actions will be defined and documented in a contingency plan. A contingency plan will be developed by the responsible partner and monitored by the Executive Board.

7 Intellectual property right issues

The IPR strategy and the exploitation management will be handled in the CA, as well as in the T6.5. The IPR strategy of the project is an important part of the project exploitation plan as proper IPR agreements need to be put in place before partners can move forward on technology adoption, commercialisation and licencing arrangements. During the project meetings the internal results will be reviewed with the goal of identifying important ideas and defining an individual strategy for the positioning of these ideas in the standardisation and commercialisation processes. The general principles for handling Knowledge and Intellectual Property Rights within RAISE are stated below and will be settled in the consortium agreement to be signed at the project start. These principles are in line with the general EC Intellectual Property Rights recommendations. Background and foreground will be clearly identified within the consortium agreement and when applicable, granting of access rights will be clearly specified. Ownership: Each participant will own the foreground it generates. Background will be clearly identified within the consortium agreement (CA) and when applicable, granting of access rights will be clearly specified. Joint ownership: When results are generated jointly, participants will seek to reach an agreement. The consortium agreement will define these rules. Protection, use and dissemination: Results capable of industrial or commercial application must be protected taking into account legitimate interests. Prior notice of dissemination must be given to other participants. Access right: Partners may define the background needed in any and manner and may exclude specific background (not necessarily prior to signature of EC grant agreement). At a preliminary stage, partners agreed on open access publishing. However, in the future, partners may also opt for gold or green access to peer-reviewed scientific publications, which might result from the project, depending on the type of information to be published.

7.1 Background

Throughout the project lifecycle, the Background IP will be used as a core resource RAISE system and the implementation of new ICT tools, but the original ownership rights will remain with the partner during and after the RAISE project. The consortium of the current project will be responsible for any transformations and use of Background IPs in new contexts, the context of RAISE 's aims, objectives, and target groups. Instead, each party shall specify all Background IP it expects to use in the course of this agreement (which is either owned by the party itself or owned by a third-party subject to license) where these IP rights, including those of third parties, existed prior to the start of this agreement or developed independently of this agreement. Prior to signing the agreement, all such disclosed lists of Background IP will be compiled and incorporated into it.

7.2 Monitoring of usage

Throughout the project, it is important to monitor the use of the background information and the results. Publicity of the background will be determined by the owner. Project members are not permitted to disclose background information outside of the project without the owner's permission. Keeping track of the usage of the background and the results produced will be the responsibility of the owner, for example, keeping download logs.

The access rights to another partner's results or background IP will only be granted if the requesting partner or consortium requires this access to complete the project or use its own results. All Access Rights are non-exclusive, worldwide, and expressly exclude any right to sub-license unless expressly stated otherwise. Each party warrants that, during the term of the agreement, they have all the rights to use any Background IP and that they are authorized to grant such licenses. The Consortium Agreement will also specify how jointly-owned IP and foreground IP will be used. A maximum of RAISE outputs will be openly available to the RAISE audience and beyond, except for IPs transferred to consortium partners interested in using them after the project is completed.

If possible, these valuable Results will be protected by their owner(s) through the filing of patent applications, or by other IP protection measures. It is the parties' responsibility to ensure that valuable Results are protected.

7.3 Transfer of results

Each partner may transfer ownership of its own results in accordance with the GA's procedures. A third party may be identified in the CA to whom it intends to transfer ownership of its results. In accordance with GA, other partners waive the right to prior notice and their right to object to a transfer to a listed third party. The transferring partner, however, shall inform other partners of such transfer at the time of such transfer, and shall ensure that such transfer will not affect the rights of other partners (see Section 8 of the CA for more information).

7.4 Dissemination of results

In order to maximize project knowledge, participants will prepare publications based on their work. According to the requirements of Horizon 2020, steps will be taken to ensure open access to peer-reviewed publications. The consortium will work in accordance with the Open Research Data Pilot's principles. The standard approach will be to follow the 'green' route to open access, which means that publications will be deposited before, alongside, or after publication. As part of the project budget, the consortium will cover the costs associated with open access publishing to facilitate dissemination and reuse. It may be necessary for participants to submit articles to journals (or proceedings) that only offer a lower level of open access, either through parallel publication or embargo.

A case-by-case evaluation will be conducted to determine whether this is necessary and to balance the benefits against the inconvenience or delay involved in accessing the results. Regardless, at least the final author's version of every accepted paper will be made publicly available in accordance with many journals' rules, such as IEEE publications. This project will utilize widely available self-archiving (or green open access) services in the research community, such as ResearchGate (or Academia), which will allow for a balancing act between traditional publications and open access. All IP assets created and planned by the project will be recorded. In addition, the project's management board will periodically review its IP asset list and determine whether exploitation paths are explored for the most valuable IP. Furthermore, RAISE will establish a simple publication notification procedure so that partners wishing to publish or otherwise disclose project activities and results can notify the other partners in advance. A lightweight publication notification and IP asset tracking procedure will be implemented, in which partners will fill out simple templates that will be shared via RAISE's document management tool, taking into account whether the planned deliverables are subject to general dissemination focus or consortium-specific classifications.

7.5 Joint ownership

Two or more partners own results jointly if they have jointly generated them and if it is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each partner, or separate them for the purposes of obtaining, maintaining, or applying for their protection (GA). It is necessary for the partners concerned to enter into a joint ownership agreement (in writing). In this agreement, the following should be addressed:

- Conditions for granting licenses (if they differ from those outlined in the GA)
- Criteria or principles for determining fair and reasonable compensation for the other joint owners, if a non-exclusive license is granted to a third party (if appropriate)
- The method by which disputes will be resolved (e.g., through mediation, the application of applicable law, etc.) where no joint ownership agreement has yet been signed.
- Joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned results for non-commercial research purposes royalty-free and without the prior consent of the other joint owner(s)
- Under the GA, joint owners automatically have the right to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties (without the right to sublicense) for the purpose of exploiting jointly (without obtaining prior consent from other joint owners)
- The joint owner that intends to grant the license must notify the other joint owners at least 45 calendar days in advance (together with adequate information to determine whether the proposed compensation is reasonable and fair).
- Joint owners may agree on different arrangements in their joint-ownership agreement.